

From Classroom to Chip Fabrication: How UPC Shapes Future Leaders in Semiconductor Engineering

Best practice category

Skills

Stakeholder group

Research and Academia

Value chain position

R&D

General Information

Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya based in **Barcelona**, is one of the leading Spanish and European technical universities, with a strong engineering tradition. In recent years, UPC has established itself as a national benchmark in advanced training for the semiconductor industry, both for the variety of degree programs and for its network of collaborations with other universities, research centres and companies.

Activities and best practices

- Among the most significant initiatives is the Master's Degree in Electronic Engineering, which offers a comprehensive approach to the sector, covering both design and semiconductor manufacturing aspects. It currently has around 60 students, with a significant number of international students (between 20% and 30%).
- The **UPC** is also promoting the new inter-university Master's Degree in Integrated Circuit Design and Manufacturing, launched in 2024 as a direct response to the growing demand for specialist skills. This master's degree course, coordinated by the UPC in collaboration with three other Catalan universities (**Universitat de Barcelona, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Universitat Rovira i Virgili**), also benefits from the strategic collaboration of the IMB-CNM, the Barcelona Institute of Microelectronics of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). The master's degree has already attracted the interest of 30 students in its first year, with prospects for expansion.
- Particular attention is paid to links with industry. Companies actively participate by offering seminars, supervising degree theses and offering curricular internships. Practical activities are also provided, such as interactive workshops and courses held in laboratory environments. This integration allows students to tackle real challenges and come into contact with the most advanced technologies at an early stage.
- In the field of photonics, the UPC collaborates with the Institute of Photonic Sciences (ICFO), one of the most advanced research centres in Europe, contributing to training in the field of quantum computing and silicon photonics.

- UPC actively participates in European projects and strategic national initiatives, such as Proyecto Estratégico de Microelectrónica y Semiconductores (PERTE) Chip, through the **University-Business Chair**, which promotes dialogue between the academic and business worlds. UPC is also a partner in the GreenChips-EDU project, which aims to make microelectronics-related subjects more appealing to students, promote academic mobility, spread knowledge developed at university level, and integrate environmental sustainability issues into teaching content, with a particular focus on **low-energy design**.

Challenges addressed with this practice

UPC faces key challenges related to the shortage of specialist semiconductor skills and the disconnect between academic training and industrial needs. Through dedicated master's degrees, collaboration with businesses and practical laboratory activities, the university helps to form highly qualified technical profiles. The initiatives promoted also respond to the need to strengthen academic mobility, integrate sustainability into curricula and make the sector more attractive for the new generations.